

Mapping Executive Function Tasks for Children: A Scoping Review for Designing a Research-Oriented Platform

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Abstract

BACKGROUND: Executive functions (EFs) are a set of cognitive processes with inhibition, working memory, and cognitive flexibility as their core components. These processes help individuals control impulses, stay focused, think before acting, and mentally handle information. Childhood is a critical period for the development of EF, and effective assessment and intervention tools play a key role in the development of these skills. However, there are few standardized tools, and not many studies combine EF tasks with physical activity in a gamified approach.

OBJECTIVES: This scoping review aims to map the existing EF tasks used for children, identify common implementation strategies, and explore methods for measuring outcomes, providing a foundation for the development of a research-oriented and structured platform to assess executive functions in childhood.

DESIGN: A systematic search was conducted in SCOPUS, ScienceDirect, and ERIC databases using the query "executive function task" AND (children OR child OR childhood)". Inclusion criteria included studies published between 2019 and 2024, written in English, with participants aged 5 to 9 years. Extracted data included details on stimuli, trials, measures, scoring mechanisms, and stop conditions. Studies were excluded if they lacked clear methodological descriptions, such as undefined stopping criteria or unspecified task adaptation methods, which compromised their comparability.

RESULTS: A total of 2044 articles were identified, with 113 duplicates removed. After selection and eligibility evaluation, 23 studies met the inclusion criteria. The list of identified tasks can be found in the table 2. The findings highlight key EF tasks, implementation strategies, and measurement methodologies.

CONCLUSIONS: Integrating EF tasks into a structured platform for children offers a promising approach to address research gaps, standardize assessments, and provide researchers with a flexible and reliable tool for studying EF development.

KEYWORDS: *Executive Functions, Inhibition, Working Memory, Cognitive Flexibility, Task Design, Standardization*

1 Introduction

Executive functions (EFs) are a set of cognitive processes responsible for **inhibition, working memory, and cognitive flexibility**. These abilities are crucial for children's *academic success, social interactions, and emotional regulation* [1]. Childhood represents a *critical period for EF development*, with significant growth occurring between the ages of **5 and 9 years** [2]. Assessing and strengthening executive functions in school-aged children is essential for promoting academic achievement and reducing educational disparities. Research has consistently demonstrated that EF skills correlate with mathematics, reading comprehension, and writing proficiency, sometimes even more strongly than IQ [3].

Recent studies highlight the importance of using fun and age-appropriate tasks to assess and improve EF skills in children [4]. However, several challenges persist. Traditional methods, such as paper-based neuropsychological tests and teacher/parent rating scales, often lack real-world applicability and cultural adaptability, making them less effective in capturing children’s everyday EF-related challenges [5].

In digital assessments, some studies **lack clarity in defining trial parameters**, such as the number of repetitions or stopping conditions, limiting their applicability across diverse contexts. Despite strong evidence supporting the benefits of physical activity for cognitive development, integration into EF tasks remains limited [6]. Additionally, there is a lack of standardized, scalable, and easily accessible tools for monitoring EF development over time.

To address these challenges, there is a growing interest in digital platforms that allow real-time, research-oriented EF assessment. Digital solutions provide advantages such as dynamic task adaptation, automated data collection, and greater accessibility across diverse educational settings, particularly for children with low levels of text comprehension [7]. Digital EF assessments enable the creation of new, game-based task implementations with customizable parameters. By allowing dynamic adjustments to stimuli, content, and difficulty levels, these systems enhance accuracy, engagement, and ecological validity. Such adaptability ensures that EF tasks can be tailored to different research needs, educational contexts, and individual cognitive profiles, making assessments more flexible, scalable, and accessible.

This scoping review aims to **map the existing EF tasks used for children**, identify **common implementation strategies**, and explore **methods for measuring outcomes**, providing a foundation for designing a structured, adaptable, and evidence-based tool that facilitates standardized EF assessments and supports educational and cognitive interventions.

2 Methods

This scoping review follows the PRISMA-ScR guidelines for scoping reviews.

2.1 Target Population

The target population consists of **children aged 5 to 9 years**. This range represents a *critical period* for the acquisition and refinement of **inhibition, working memory, and cognitive flex-**

ibility, aligning with key *educational milestones* from *preschool to early primary education* [1, 4].

2.2 Research Questions

1. **What types of executive function tasks are commonly used for children?**
2. **What are the main strategies for applying these tasks to children?**
3. **How are these tasks used to measure and enhance executive functions in children?**

2.3 Search Strategy and Study Selection

The search strategy was designed to identify studies published between **2019 and 2024**. This time frame was chosen to ensure that the review captures the most recent developments in executive function (EF) assessment methods while maintaining a manageable scope, allowing for a more feasible data collection process, and still ensuring the inclusion of studies reflecting current research trends. Additionally, as digital and gamified EF assessments have evolved rapidly in recent years, focusing on the most recent literature helps highlight the latest advancements in the field.

The study selection process adhered to PRISMA guidelines. The flow chart (Figure 1) details the stages from identification to inclusion.

2.4 Data Extraction

Data extraction focused on:

- **Study Characteristics:** Author(s), year, and design.
- **Population Details:** Age range.
- **Task Details:** Task type, target EF, objectives.
- **Task Implementation:** Stimuli, trials, measures, scoring, stop conditions.

3 Results

3.1 Executive Function Tasks Identified

The selected studies included multiple executive function tasks. Many of the articles provided rich details about the tasks implementation and many of them used more than one tasks in the study.

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram for Executive Function Task Review (Children Aged 5-9).

Below, in the table 2, each study is listed along with the tasks name, their objectives, stimuli, and some implementation details.

The studies reviewed reveal a variety of tasks used to assess core executive functions in children. These tasks measure aspects such as inhibition, working memory, and cognitive flexibility. For instance, tasks like the Flanker and Go/No-Go Task primarily assess inhibition, requiring participants to focus on specific targets while ignoring distractors or suppressing responses to certain stimuli. These tasks are typically implemented using visual stimuli, such as arrows or animals, presented on a computer screen or physical cards, and include a series of trials with varying difficulty levels.

For working memory, tasks like the Backward Digit Span and the Corsi Blocks Backward Task were common, requiring children to recall sequences in reverse order. These tasks use auditory or visual sequences and challenge children by increasing sequence length as they progress. The Dimensional Change Card Sort (DCCS) task is key for assessing cognitive flexibility. It requires children to switch sorting rules based on color or shape, testing their ability to adapt to changing rules.

Many tasks use block-based designs, dividing trials into practice, test, and mixed sections, with increasing difficulty. These designs assess baseline performance while challenging children with variations in stimuli to test adaptability and learning

abilities.

Most studies employed visual stimuli, with some using auditory cues or multisensory elements to engage children. The variety of stimuli types demonstrates the flexibility of these tasks in assessing different executive functions and how sensory modalities may influence performance.

Even with different methods, common measures were used, including reaction time (RT), accuracy, and performance metrics like error rates or interference scores. These measures provide valuable insights into the child’s cognitive abilities and their management of task demands and distractions.

3.2 Summary of Key Findings

This scoping review provides a comprehensive analysis of the executive function (EF) tasks used in children aged 5-9 years, highlighting the diversity of tasks across studies. A total of 28 distinct EF tasks were identified, with several variations in their implementation.

Cognitive flexibility tasks, such as the Dimensional Change Card Sort (DCCS) and the Wisconsin Card Sorting Task (WCST), assess a child’s ability to shift between rules and adapt thinking. Inhibitory control was primarily assessed using the Flanker Task and Go/No-Go Task, both measuring the ability to focus attention and suppress responses to irrelevant stimuli. These tasks often had slight variations in stimuli, such as arrows or fish, but shared the core goal of measuring inhibition.

Working memory tasks, like the Backward Digit Span and Working Memory Task, typically involved recalling sequences of numbers or visual locations, assessing short-term memory and the ability to manipulate information. Additionally, tasks like the Head-Toes-Knees-Shoulders (HTKS) and DCCS measured both inhibition and cognitive flexibility.

Many studies employed tasks with mixed cognitive demands, such as those that combined cognitive flexibility, inhibition, and working memory, highlighting the interconnected nature of these functions. Tasks like the Stroop Task had different versions, but all aimed to measure a child’s ability to control automatic responses.

Stimuli were diverse, with visual cues such as arrows and animals being common, though auditory signals were also used. The variety of stimuli shows the adaptability of EF tasks to engage children with different learning styles and ensure reliable results.

In summary, the review identifies the most common EF tasks for children aged 5-9 years, emphasizing that small variations in task design can

assess similar cognitive processes like inhibition, cognitive flexibility, and working memory.

4 Limitations

This review has some limitations that should be acknowledged.

One of the main constraints concerns the age range criterion (5–9 years) used for study inclusion. This restriction may have excluded studies with executive function tasks aimed at younger children, particularly those designed for 4-year-olds. Such tasks might have provided valuable insights into developmental transitions or specific adaptations necessary for creating age-appropriate tools and platforms.

Additionally, the review focused on studies published between 2019 and 2024. While this approach ensured an up-to-date analysis, it may have unintentionally excluded older yet still relevant research that could offer important theoretical or methodological contributions. However, these decisions were essential to maintain a manageable scope and enable a thorough analysis within the available resources.

5 Discussion

The findings from this scoping review highlight both the progress and persistent challenges in the assessment of executive functions (EF) in children. While a variety of tasks have been developed to measure inhibition, working memory, and cognitive flexibility, substantial inconsistencies exist in their **implementation, trial parameters, and scoring methods**. These discrepancies pose significant barriers to the **comparability of results across studies**, ultimately limiting the field’s ability to establish robust conclusions regarding EF development.

To better illustrate the landscape of EF assessments, Table 1 provides a structured classification of tasks according to their primary EF component—Inhibitory Control, Working Memory, or Cognitive Flexibility. This categorization highlights the diversity of tasks used in research and reveals an uneven distribution of EF components, with some functions receiving significantly more focus than others. Furthermore, Table 2 presents a comprehensive synthesis of EF tasks, detailing their methodologies, implementation strategies, and scoring mechanisms, reinforcing the methodological inconsistencies across studies. These insights emphasize the need for a more standardized and structured approach to EF task design

and implementation.

5.1 Lack of Standardization Across Studies

One of the main issues identified is the **lack of consistency in task parameters**, even for widely used assessments. Tasks such as the *Flanker Task*, *Go/No-Go Task*, and *Dimensional Change Card Sort (DCCS)* exhibit considerable **variations in trial lengths, block structures, and response criteria**, which directly impact the difficulty and interpretation of results. For example, in the *Go/No-Go Task*, the proportion of “go” versus “no-go” trials varies across studies, affecting inhibitory demands and making comparisons difficult. Similarly, in the *Flanker Task*, discrepancies in stimulus presentation times and response deadlines lead to inconsistent difficulty levels across implementations.

Beyond these technical aspects, scoring criteria also differ widely. Some tasks, particularly those embedded in standardized cognitive batteries (e.g., *Backward Digit Span*), benefit from well-established norms, allowing results to be contextualized within broader developmental frameworks. However, many other EF tasks lack reference data, making it unclear **how performance should be interpreted across different samples and cultural settings**. Without standardized guidelines, results remain difficult to compare, limiting the generalizability of EF research.

5.2 The Need for a Unified Framework

Given these challenges, a structured and **standardized digital platform** is necessary to enhance the comparability and reliability of EF assessments. Such a platform would serve to:

- **Standardize task implementation** – Define fixed parameters for trial numbers, timing, and scoring to ensure consistency across studies.
- **Ensure cross-cultural applicability** – Adapt tasks to different linguistic and educational contexts while maintaining their core cognitive demands.
- **Facilitate large-scale data collection** – Allow researchers to gather and compare EF performance across diverse populations with greater methodological rigor.
- **Integrate physical activity into digital assessments** – Many EF tasks remain

static, despite evidence that **motor engagement enhances cognitive performance** [6]. A modern framework should explore **ways to incorporate movement-based tasks digitally**, using motion tracking, adaptive feedback, or hybrid digital-physical designs.

Tasks that are highly structured and **less dependent on environmental context**, such as the *Flanker Task*, *DCCS*, and *Go/No-Go Task*, are well-suited for digital adaptation and could serve as the foundation for a standardized framework. In contrast, **movement-based EF tasks**, such as *HTKS* and *Freeze Task*, require innovative **digital adaptations** to preserve their cognitive and motor demands while ensuring consistency across studies.

Additionally, some tasks present specific characteristics that make them particularly promising for digital adaptation. For **inhibitory control**, tasks such as the *Stroop Task*, *Flanker Task*, and *Go/No-Go Task* have well-established methodologies and are widely implemented in computerized settings. In the case of **working memory**, tasks like the *Backward Digit Span*, *Corsi Blocks Task*, and *Keep Track Task* provide reliable cognitive measures and can be effectively implemented in digital formats with minimal modifications. Finally, for **cognitive flexibility**, the *Dimensional Change Card Sort (DCCS)*, *Wisconsin Card Sorting Task (WCST)*, and *Dots Task* offer strong candidates for digital transformation due to their structured nature and adaptability to automated scoring.

5.3 Conclusion

The extensive **variability in EF task design and administration** underscores the urgent need for a **standardized framework** to improve research reliability and applicability. Furthermore, the **underutilization of movement-based tasks**, despite their **proven cognitive benefits**, highlights an area for innovation in EF assessment. The development of a **research-oriented digital platform** offers a **practical solution** to these methodological inconsistencies, ensuring that EF assessments are comparable, replicable, and accessible across diverse research contexts. By integrating **well-defined parameters, standardized scoring mechanisms, and adaptable task designs—including movement-based elements in a digital format**—this platform has the potential to **bridge existing gaps** in EF assessment and advance our understanding of cognitive development in children.

References

- [1] Adele Diamond. Executive functions. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 64(Volume 64, 2013):135–168, 2013. ISSN 1545-2085. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-113011-143750>. URL <https://www.annualreviews.org/content/journals/10.1146/annurev-psych-113011-143750>.
- [2] Akira Miyake and Naomi P. Friedman. The nature and organization of individual differences in executive functions: Four general conclusions. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 21(1):8–14, 2012. doi: [10.1177/0963721411429458](https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721411429458). URL <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721411429458>. PMID: 22773897.
- [3] Shelley Shaul, Mila Schwartz, Shelley Shaul, and · Schwartz. The role of the executive functions in school readiness among preschool-age children. *Reading and Writing*, 27, 08 2013. doi: [10.1007/s11145-013-9470-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11145-013-9470-3).
- [4] John R. Best and Patricia H. Miller. A developmental perspective on executive function. *Child Development*, 81(6):1641–1660, 2010. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2010.01499.x>. URL <https://srcd.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2010.01499.x>.
- [5] Jill Fahy. Assessment of executive functions in school-aged children: Challenges and solutions for the slp. *Perspectives on School-Based Issues*, 15:151, 12 2014. doi: [10.1044/sbi15.4.151](https://doi.org/10.1044/sbi15.4.151).
- [6] Phillip D. Tomporowski, Bryan McCullick, Daniel M. Pendleton, and Caterina Pesce. Exercise and children’s cognition: The role of exercise characteristics and a place for metacognition. *Journal of Sport and Health Science*, 4(1):47–55, 2015. ISSN 2095-2546. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jshs.2014.09.003>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2095254614001203>.
- [7] Costanza Ruffini, Christian Tarchi, and Chiara Pecini. Which executive functions affect text comprehension and writing in paper and digital mode? an investigation in primary school children. *Computers Education*, 207:104936, 09 2023. doi: [10.1016/j.compedu.2023.104936](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2023.104936).

- [8] Elien Bellon, Wim Fias, and Bert De Smedt. More than number sense: The additional role of executive functions and metacognition in arithmetic. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 182:38–60, 2019. ISSN 0022-0965. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2019.01.012>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022096517306033>.
- [9] K. Lertladaluck and Y. Moriguchi. Executive functions and theory of mind development in preschoolers: Insights from nirs data. *Neuropsychologia*, 205:109031, 2024. ISSN 0028-3932. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2024.109031>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S002839322400246X>.
- [10] Brenna Lin, Jeffrey Liew, and Marisol Perez. Measurement of self-regulation in early childhood: Relations between laboratory and performance-based measures of effortful control and executive functioning. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 47:1–8, 2019. ISSN 0885-2006. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2018.10.004>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0885200618301194>.
- [11] Athanasia Papastergiou, Eirini Sanoudaki, Marco Tamburelli, and Vasiliki Chondrogianni. A study on the executive functioning skills of greek–english bilingual children – a nearest neighbour approach. *Bilingualism: Language and Cognition*, 26(1):78–94, 2023. doi: 10.1017/S1366728922000335.
- [12] Katharina Schirmbeck, Nirmala Rao, Rhoda Wang, Ben Richards, Stephanie W. Y. Chan, and Claudia Maehler. Contrasting executive function development among primary school children from Hong Kong and Germany. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 36(4):923–943, December 2021. ISSN 1878-5174. doi: 10.1007/s10212-020-00519-9. URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-020-00519-9>.
- [13] Edy Veneziano and Eleonora Bartoli. Individual differences in the effectiveness of a narrative-promoting intervention: Relation with executive function skills. *First Language*, 42(4):523–547, 2022. doi: 10.1177/01427237221092661. URL <https://doi.org/10.1177/01427237221092661>.
- [14] Theodore P. Zanto, Anastasia Gianakopoulou, Courtney L. Gallen, Avery E. Ostrand, Jessica W. Younger, Roger Anguera-Singla, Joaquin A. Anguera, and Adam Gazzaley. Digital rhythm training improves reading fluency in children. *Developmental Science*, 27(3):e13473, 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/desc.13473>. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/desc.13473>.
- [15] Amanda Grenell, Jacob R. Butts, Susan C. Levine, and Emily R. Fyfe. Children’s confidence on mathematical equivalence and fraction problems. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 246:106003, 2024. ISSN 0022-0965. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2024.106003>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022096524001437>.
- [16] Michelle N. Maurer and Claudia M. Roebers. Towards a better understanding of the association between motor skills and executive functions in 5- to 6-year-olds: The impact of motor task difficulty. *Human Movement Science*, 66:607–620, 2019. ISSN 0167-9457. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.humov.2019.06.010>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167945718308583>.
- [17] Niamh Oeri and Claudia M. Roebers. Regulating disappointment can impair cognitive performance in kindergarten children: Individual differences in ego depletion. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 190:104728, 2020. ISSN 0022-0965. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2019.104728>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022096518305903>.
- [18] Dilara Keşşafoglu, Aylin Küntay, and Berna A. Uzundağ. Immediate and delayed effects of fantastical content on children’s executive functions and mental transformation. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 248:106067, 2024. ISSN 0022-0965. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2024.106067>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022096524002078>.
- [19] Lydia Lavis and Caitlin E.V. Mahy. “i’ll remember everything no matter what!”: The role of metacognitive abilities in the development of young children’s prospective memory. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 207:105117, 2021. ISSN 0022-0965. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2021.105117>.

- 10.1016/j.jecp.2021.105117. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022096521000357>.
- [20] Laura Traverso, Irene Tonizzi, M. Carmen Usai, and Paola Viterbori. The relationship of working memory and inhibition with different number knowledge skills in preschool children. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 203:105014, 2021. ISSN 0022-0965. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2020.105014>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022096520304689>.
- [21] Jonas Schäfer, Timo Reuter, Miriam Leuchter, and Julia Karbach. Executive functions and problem-solving—the contribution of inhibition, working memory, and cognitive flexibility to science problem-solving performance in elementary school students. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 244:105962, 2024. ISSN 0022-0965. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2024.105962>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022096524001024>.
- [22] Sha Xie, Shuqi Lu, Jiahao Lu, Chaohui Gong, and Chunqi Chang. Using mindfulness-based intervention to promote executive function in young children: a multivariable and multi-scale sample entropy study. *Cerebral Cortex*, 34(9):bhae330, 09 2024. ISSN 1460-2199. doi: [10.1093/cercor/bhae330](https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhae330). URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhae330>.
- [23] Sha Xie, Chaohui Gong, Jiahao Lu, Hui Li, Dandan Wu, Xinli Chi, and Chunqi Chang. Enhancing chinese preschoolers' executive function via mindfulness training: An fnirs study. *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience*, 16, 2022. ISSN 1662-5153. doi: [10.3389/fnbeh.2022.961797](https://doi.org/10.3389/fnbeh.2022.961797). URL <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/behavioral-neuroscience/articles/10.3389/fnbeh.2022.961797>.
- [24] Ebru Ger and Florian J. Buehler. Is monitoring in executive functions related to metacognitive monitoring? *Cognitive Development*, 72:101514, 2024. ISSN 0885-2014. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogdev.2024.101514>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0885201424000996>.
- [25] Ebru Ger and Claudia M. Roebers. Monitoring and control processes within executive functions: Is post-error slowing related to pre-error speeding in children? *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 246:105975, 2024. ISSN 0022-0965. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2024.105975>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022096524001152>.
- [26] Sammy F. Ahmed, Jennie Grammer, and Frederick Morrison. Cognition in context: Validating group-based executive function assessments in young children. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 208:105131, 2021. ISSN 0022-0965. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2021.105131>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022096521000497>.
- [27] Hedi Kwakkel, Mienke Droop, Ludo Verhoeven, and Eliane Segers. The impact of lexical skills and executive functioning on l1 and l2 phonological awareness in bilingual kindergarten. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 88:102009, 2021. ISSN 1041-6080. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2021.102009>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1041608021000467>.
- [28] Moeko Ishikawa, Yusuke Moriguchi, and Yasuhiro Kanakogi. Relationship between executive function and persistence in 5-year-olds. *Cognitive Development*, 67:101361, 2023. ISSN 0885-2014. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogdev.2023.101361>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0885201423000667>.
- [29] Jianhua Zhang, Jiacheng Lu, Youbin Sun, and Ji Li. Recreational gymnastics exercise of moderate intensity enhances executive function in chinese preschoolers: A randomized controlled trial. *PsyCh Journal*, 13(6):954–965, 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/pchj.786>. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/pchj.786>.
- [30] Shi Yu Chan, Zi Yan Ong, Zhen Ming Ngho, Yap Seng Chong, Juan H. Zhou, Marielle V. Fortier, Lourdes M. Daniel, Anqi Qiu, Michael J. Meaney, and Ai Peng Tan. Structure-function coupling within the reward network in preschool children predicts executive functioning in later childhood. *Developmental Cognitive Neuroscience*, 55:101107, 2022. ISSN 1878-9293. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dcn.2022.101107>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1878929322000107>.

[//www.sciencedirect.com/science/
article/pii/S1878929322000500.](http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1878929322000500)

Appendix

Table 1: Executive Function Tasks Categorized by EF Component

Task	Author(s)	Year	Age Range/Mean	Notes
Inhibitory Control - 18 tasks				
Stroop Task (7)	Bellon et al. [8]	2019	6–8 years	Animal Stroop Task
	Lertladaluck et al. [9]	2024	5–7 years	
	Lin et al. [10]	2019	≈ 5 years	Shape Stroop Task Nonverbal Stroop Task
	Papastergiou et al. [11]	2022	5–9 years	
	Schirmbeck et al. [12]	2021	8–10 years	Child-Friendly Stroop Task
	Veneziano et al. [13]	2022	6–8 years	Animal Stroop Task
Zanto et al. [14]	2024	8–9 years		
Flanker Task (6)	Bellon et al. [8]	2019	6–8 years	
	Grenell et al. [15]	2024	7–9 years	
	Lertladaluck et al. [9]	2024	5–7 years	
	Maurer et al. [16]	2019	5–6 years	
	Oeri et al. [17]	2020	5–6 years	
	Zanto et al. [14]	2024	8–9 years	
Simon Says Task (3)	Keşsafoğlu et al. [18]	2024	5–6 years	
	Lavis et al. [19]	2021	≈ 5 years	
	Traverso et al. [20]	2021	5–6 years	
Go/No-Go Task (3)	Schäfer et al. [21]	2024	6–8 years	
	Xie et al. [22]	2024	5–6 years	
	Xie et al. [23]	2022	5–6 years	
Hearts and Flowers Task (2)	Ger et al. [24]	2024	6–8 years	This task also involves cognitive flexibility.
	Ger et al. [25]	2024	6–8 years	
Head-Toes-Knees-Shoulders (2)	Ahmed et al. [26]	2020	5–6 years	This task also involves working memory.
	Kwakkel et al. [27]	2021	5–6 years	
Freeze Task (1)	Ahmed et al. [26]	2020	5–6 years	
Jumping Task (1)	Ahmed et al. [26]	2020	5–6 years	
Pair Cancellation Task (1)	Ahmed et al. [26]	2020	5–6 years	
Red/Blue Task (1)	Ishikawa et al. [28]	2023	5–6 years	
Bear/Dragon (1)	Ishikawa et al. [28]	2023	5–6 years	
Continuous Performance Task (1)	Kwakkel et al. [27]	2021	5–6 years	
Luria Hand Game (1)	Lertladaluck et al. [9]	2024	5–7 years	
Snack Delay Task (1)	Lin et al. [10]	2019	≈ 5 years	
Toy Delay Task (1)	Lin et al. [10]	2019	≈ 5 years	
Preschool Matching Familiar Figure Task (1)	Traverso et al. [20]	2021	5–6 years	
Stop Signal Task (1)	Zhang et al. [29]	2024	5–6 years	
Marching Task (1)	Ahmed et al. [26]	2020	5–6 years	

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Task	Author(s)	Year	Age Range/Mean	Notes
Working Memory - 12 tasks				
Backward Digit/Word Span (4)	Ahmed et al. [26]	2020	5–6 years	
	Papastergiou et al. [11]	2022	5–9 years	
	Keşsafoğlu et al. [18]	2024	5–6 years	
	Lavis et al. [19]	2021	≈ 5 years	
Working Memory Task (2)	Xie et al. [22]	2024	5–6 years	
	Zanto et al. [14]	2024	8–9 years	
Keep Track Task (2)	Traverso et al. [20]	2021	5–6 years	
	Zhang et al. [29]	2024	5–6 years	
Forward Word Span (1)	Kwakkel et al. [27]	2021	5–6 years	
Animal Updating Task (1)	Maurer et al. [16]	2019	5–6 years	
2-Back Task (1)	Bellon et al. [8]	2019	6–8 years	
Object Span Task (1)	Schirmbeck et al. [12]	2021	8–10 years	
Corsi Blocks Backward Task (1)	Schäfer et al. [21]	2024	6–8 years	
Dual Request Selective Task (1)	Traverso et al. [20]	2021	5–6 years	
Missing Scan Task (1)	Xie et al. [23]	2022	5–6 years	
Letter Memory Task (1)	Zhang et al. [29]	2024	5–6 years	
List Sorting Task (1)	Grenell et al. [15]	2024	7–9 years	
Cognitive Flexibility - 8 tasks				
Dimensional Change Card Sort (DCCS) (5)	Grenell et al. [15]	2024	7–9 years	
	Ishikawa et al. [28]	2023	5–6 years	
	Maurer et al. [16]	2019	5–6 years	
	Xie et al. [22]	2024	5–6 years	
	Xie et al. [23]	2022	5–6 years	
Wisconsin Card Sorting Task (WCST) (2)	Bellon et al. [8]	2019	6–8 years	
	Chan et al. [30]	2022	≈ 5 years	
Flexible Item Selection (2)	Keşsafoğlu et al. [18]	2024	5–6 years	
	Schäfer et al. [21]	2024	6–8 years	
Colour-Shape Task (1)	Papastergiou et al. [11]	2022	5–9 years	
Classification Task (1)	Veneziano et al. [13]	2022	6–8 years	

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Task	Author(s)	Year	Age Range/Mean	Notes
Local/Global Task (1)	Veneziano et al. [13]	2022	6–8 years	
Dots Task (1)	Zhang et al. [29]	2024	5–6 years	
Minnesota Executive Function Scale (MEFS) (1)	Oeri et al. [17]	2020	5–6 years	This task also involves working memory and inhibitory control.

Table 2: Summary of Executive Function Tasks from Included Studies (5–9 years)

Author(s)	Year	Task	Target EF	Objective	Stimulus	Trials
Ahmed et al. [26]	2020	Freeze Task Jumping Task Marching Task Head-Toes-Knees-Shoulders Backward Digit Span Pair Cancellation Task	Inhibitory Control Inhibitory Control, Working Memory Inhibitory Control, Cognitive Flexibility Inhibitory Control Working Memory Inhibitory Control	Children march in a circle and freeze when music starts. They unfreeze when instructed or when music stops. Children follow one- to three-step instructions after freezing (e.g., jump three times, clap twice). Children march in one direction for a specific song and the opposite direction for another song. Children perform the opposite of the instructed movement (e.g., touch toes when asked to touch head). Children repeat numbers in reverse order. Children identify specific pairs (e.g., a ball followed by a dog) on a stimulus sheet.	Music played for random intervals (7–15 seconds) Music played for random intervals (7–15 seconds) Music played for random intervals (7–15 seconds) Not specified Spoken sequences of numbers Rows of pictures on a sheet	5 trials (Stop time: Reaction to freezing and distractibility) 3 trials (Stop time, distractibility, action recall, action performance) 7 trials (Stop time, distractibility, march recall, march performance) 30 trials across 3 blocks Not specified Not specified
Bellon et al. [8]	2019	Flanker Task	Inhibitory Control	Assess inhibition by responding to a central arrow's direction while ignoring flanking distractors.	Arrows flanked by distractors, presented for 2500 ms and black screen visible for 1000 ms	40 test trials (50% incongruent), preceded by 12 baseline trials with single arrows.

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Author(s)	Year	Task	Target EF	Objective	Stimulus	Trials
		Animal Stroop Task	Inhibitory Control	Assess inhibition by identifying the larger animal in real life, ignoring image size.	Two animals presented simultaneously, with one image four times larger. Stimuli appeared for 2000 ms, followed by a black screen that remained visible for 1000 ms	40 test trials (50% incongruent), preceded by 20 baseline trials with equal-sized images.
		Wisconsin Card Sorting Task (WCST)	Cognitive Flexibility	Measure cognitive flexibility by sorting cards based on changing rules (color or shape).	Cards with specific colors and shapes.	50 trials; sorting rule changes after 7–9 correct responses.
		2-Back Task	Working Memory	Measure updating by identifying if a current stimulus matches one shown two trials earlier.	Colored images, presented for 3000 ms each followed by black screen that remained visible for 1000 ms	40 test trials, with 30% being targets.
Chan et al. [30]	2022	Wisconsin Card Sorting Task (WCST)	Cognitive Flexibility	Measure cognitive flexibility by switching rules in categorization tasks.	Cards with attributes of color, shape, and number; rules change after 10 consecutive correct responses.	64 total trials.
Ger et al. [24]	2024	Hearts and Flowers Task	Inhibitory Control, Cognitive flexibility	Assess inhibition and cognitive flexibility through rule-switching.	Geometric shapes (hearts and flowers); heart = congruent, flower = incongruent.	Hearts: 24, Flowers: 36, Mixed: 48 (with 12 flowers).
Ger et al. [25]	2024	Hearts and Flowers Task	Inhibitory Control, Cognitive Flexibility	Assess inhibitory control and cognitive flexibility.	Stimuli presented on a screen: Hearts (congruent) and Flowers (incongruent). Each trial has 750 ms stimulus duration, followed by a 500 ms fixation cross.	Block 1: 24 congruent trials; Block 2: 36 incongruent trials; Block 3: 48 congruent + 12 incongruent trials.
Grenell et al. [15]	2024	Flanker Task	Inhibitory Control	Measure inhibitory control and attention.	Five fish or arrows; central target's direction is identified (e.g., iiiii or iiiii).	Not specified; includes congruent and incongruent trials.

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Author(s)	Year	Task	Target EF	Objective	Stimulus	Trials
		List Sorting Task	Working Memory	Measure working memory by recalling sequences of items by category and size.	Visual presentation of items (e.g., animals, foods).	6 levels (2-7 items).
		Dimensional Change Card Sort (DCCS)	Cognitive Flexibility	Measure cognitive flexibility by switching between sorting by shape or color.	Cards with objects of varying shapes and colors.	Practice trials followed by test trials (number not specified).
Ishikawa et al. [28]	2023	Red/Blue Task	Inhibitory Control	Measure inhibitory control through responses to incongruent color names.	Cards colored red or blue; children must point to the opposite color when named by the experimenter.	10 test trials (5 red, 5 blue).
		Bear/Dragon Task	Inhibitory Control	Measure inhibitory control by following commands from the "bear" and inhibiting those from the "dragon".	Commands issued by two puppets (bear and dragon).	12 trials (6 per puppet).
		DCCS Task	Cognitive Flexibility	Assess cognitive flexibility through rule-switching in card sorting.	Cards with two dimensions (color and shape); sorted based on alternating rules.	8 trials per phase (Pre-, Post-Switch, Mixed).
		Backward Word Span	Working Memory	Measure working memory by recalling words in reverse order.	Verbal sequences of 2-5 words (e.g., "curtain, garden").	8 test trials.
		Simon Says Task	Inhibitory Control	Assess inhibitory control via selective imitation and non-imitation of commands.	Actions (e.g., touch your nose) given with or without "Simon Says."	10 trials (5 imitation, 5 anti-imitation).
		Flexible Item Selection	Cognitive Flexibility	Measure cognitive flexibility by selecting cards matching on varying dimensions.	Three cards per trial; select two matching on one dimension, then another.	15 trials.

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Author(s)	Year	Task	Target EF	Objective	Stimulus	Trials
Kwakkel et al. [27]	2021	Head-Toes-Knees-Shoulders (HTKS) Continuous Performance Task (CPT) Forward Word Span	Inhibitory Control, Working Memory Inhibitory Control Working Memory	Measure self-regulation by responding oppositely to commands. Measure sustained attention using go/no-go responses. Measure working memory by recalling word sequences.	Verbal commands like "Touch your head"; responses must be opposite (e.g., touch toes). Visual task: target = red circle, non-target = red square; auditory task: high/low tones. Spoken words in sequences of 2-7.	20 test items (10 per rule set). 200 trials per task (80 target, 120 non-target). 2 trials per sequence length.
Lavis et al. [19]	2021	Simon Task Backward Word Span Task	Inhibitory Control Working Memory	Assess inhibition by following commands only when preceded by "Simon Says." Measure working memory by repeating verbal sequences in reverse order.	Verbal instructions to perform actions, sometimes preceded by "Simon Says." Words presented verbally by the experimenter.	10 trials (5 inhibition trials). 2 trials per sequence length (2-5 words).
Lertladaluck et al. [9]	2024	Stroop Task Luria Hand Game Flanker Task	Inhibitory Control Inhibitory Control Inhibitory Control	Measure cognitive inhibition by responding to shape rather than color. Measure inhibition through congruent/incongruent hand gestures. Assess inhibition and selective visual attention by ignoring adjacent distractors.	Shapes (circle, triangle, square) shown in congruent/incongruent colors; response via touchscreen. Experimenter makes gestures (fist/point); child must mimic or do opposite depending on the session. Fish symbols pointing congruently or incongruently to the central target.	6 blocks (18 trials each: 9 congruent, 9 incongruent). 8 trials per session (congruent/incongruent). 20 trials (10 congruent, 10 incongruent).
Lin et al. [10]	2019	Shape Stroop Task	Cognitive Flexibility, Inhibitory Control	Measure cognitive flexibility and inhibition by identifying subdominant visual features.	Cards displaying shapes embedded within other shapes.	24 trials.

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Author(s)	Year	Task	Target EF	Objective	Stimulus	Trials
		Snack Delay Task	Inhibitory Control	Measure inhibitory control and delay of gratification using edible stimuli.	Transparent cup covering an M&M candy; delay durations of 10, 20, 30, and 15 seconds.	4 trials.
		Toy Delay Task	Inhibitory Control	Measure inhibitory control and delay of gratification using non-edible stimuli.	Transparent cup covering "silly bandz"; delay durations of 10, 20, 30, and 15 seconds.	4 trials.
Maurer et al. [16]	2019	Flanker Task Animal Updating Task Advanced Dimensional Change Card Sort (DCCS)	Inhibitory Control Working Memory Cognitive Flexibility	Measure inhibition by focusing on a target while ignoring distractors. Measure working memory updating by recalling the last two animals shown. Measure cognitive flexibility by sorting cards by color, shape, or a switching rule.	Visual stimuli: Fish pointing in congruent or incongruent directions. Sequences of animals presented for 1900 ms each, followed by a question mark. Cards with colors and shapes; instructions change across blocks (e.g., sort by shape if star is present).	Block 1: 20 congruent; Block 2: 20 congruent + 20 incongruent. 2 test blocks of 5 trials each. Block 1: 10 color; Block 2: 10 shape; Block 3: 20 mixed (shape if star present).
Oeri et al. [17]	2020	Minnesota Executive Function Scale (MEFS) Flanker Task	Cognitive Flexibility, Working Memory, Inhibitory Control	Assess cognitive flexibility, working memory, and inhibition through card sorting tasks. Measure response inhibition by identifying the orientation of a central target amidst distractors.	Cards sorted by changing rules (color vs. shape); increasing difficulty across 7 levels. Fish stimuli: congruent (all fish face the same way) or incongruent (target faces opposite).	5 trials per part (A and B); adaptive difficulty. 24 trials (12 congruent, 12 incongruent).
Papastergiou et al. [11]	2022	Nonverbal Stroop Task Backward Digit Span Task	Inhibitory Control Working Memory	Measure inhibition by identifying arrow directions irrespective of position. Assess updating by recalling numbers in reverse order.	Arrows pointing in different directions; congruent and incongruent blocks. Auditory presentation of number sequences.	3 blocks of 60 trials. 4–8 numbers per trial, increasing gradually.

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Author(s)	Year	Task	Target EF	Objective	Stimulus	Trials
Schäfer et al. [21]	2024	Colour-Shape Task Go/No-Go Task Corsi Blocks Backward Task Flexible Item Selection Task (FIST)	Inhibitory Control, Cognitive Flexibility Inhibitory Control Working Memory Cognitive Flexibility	Evaluate shifting between color and shape categorization tasks. Assess inhibition by responding to go stimuli and withholding for no-go stimuli. Measure working memory by recalling sequences of highlighted blocks in reverse order. Assess cognitive flexibility through categorization shifts based on new shared properties.	Shapes (circle/triangle) in different colors (red/blue) presented in top or bottom halves. Animal images (cow = No-Go, chicken/pig/donkey = Go) presented sequentially for 500 ms each. 3x3 grid; fairy images highlight blocks in increasing sequence lengths (1–8 blocks). Images sharing one or two properties (e.g., color, shape).	3 blocks: 32 trials (single-task blocks) + 64 trials (mixed-task block). 60 Go trials, 20 No-Go trials. 6 sequences per length. 18 one-commonality trials; 9 two-commonality trials.
Schirmbeck et al. [12]	2021	Child-Friendly Stroop Task Object Span Task	Inhibitory Control Working Memory	Assess cognitive inhibition by overriding automatic responses. Measure working memory by recalling sequences of objects while performing a secondary task.	Colored shapes, fruits, and vegetables; congruent and incongruent color pairings. Cards with images of objects (e.g., apple, basket); "edible or not?" secondary task.	4 sets (20 items per set). 5 trials with spans increasing (2–6 objects).
Traverso et al. [20]	2021	Keep Track Task Dual Request Selective Task	Working Memory Working Memory	Measure WM updating by recalling the last items in designated categories. Assess visual-spatial WM by recalling positions while performing a concurrent task.	Pictures from five categories (animals, sky, fruit, vehicles, clothes). Frog pathway on a 4x4 chessboard; clap when frog jumps on a red square.	6 trials: first 3 with one category; last 3 with two categories. 10 trials, increasing difficulty (pathway lengths = 2–6).

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Author(s)	Year	Task	Target EF	Objective	Stimulus	Trials
Veneziano et al. [13]	2022	Simon Task	Inhibitory Control	Measure inhibitory control by performing actions only when prompted by "Simon says."	Verbal commands with gestures.	10 trials.
		Preschool Matching Familiar Figure Task	Inhibitory Control	Assess impulsive behavior by comparing target figures to alternatives.	Target figures with five alternatives on a page.	14 trials.
		Animal Stroop Task	Inhibitory Control	Assess inhibition by naming animal bodies while ignoring faces.	Boards with congruent, control-face, and incongruent animal drawings.	3 boards (24 items each).
Xie et al. [22]	2024	Classification Task	Cognitive Flexibility	Measure cognitive flexibility by categorizing objects by different criteria.	9 wooden pieces differing in shape, color, and size; 3 containers for sorting.	3 sorting trials.
		Local/Global Task	Cognitive Flexibility	Assess flexibility in recognizing global vs. local shapes.	Boards with geometric figures containing smaller shapes within their outlines.	6 boards.
		Dimensional Change Card Sort (DCCS) Go/No-Go Task	Cognitive Flexibility	Assess cognitive flexibility by sorting cards based on changing rules.	Cards with two attributes (color and shape).	4 blocks (8 randomized trials per block).
Xie et al. [23]	2022	Working Memory Task	Inhibitory Control	Measure inhibition by responding to "Go" stimuli and withholding for "No-Go."	Images of animals (e.g., cows, horses, tigers); dog = "No-Go."	3 blocks (16 Go, 4 No-Go trials per block).
		Dimensional Change Card Sort (DCCS)	Working Memory	Measure ability to recall visual-spatial locations.	A monkey appearing on one of six trees; recall the location after the image disappears.	3 blocks (8 trials each).
Xie et al. [23]	2022	Dimensional Change Card Sort (DCCS)	Cognitive Flexibility	Assess cognitive shifting by sorting cards based on changing rules.	Target cards (red boat, blue rabbit) vs. test cards (blue boat, red rabbit).	3 sessions, each with pre- and post-switch phases (25s each).

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Author(s)	Year	Task	Target EF	Objective	Stimulus	Trials
		Go/No-Go Task Missing Scan Task	Inhibitory Control Working Memory	Measure inhibitory control by responding to "Go" stimuli and withholding for "No-Go." Measure working memory by identifying missing objects after a brief presentation.	Animal images (cow, horse, tiger = "Go"; dog = "No-Go"). Sets of 4 animals displayed for 10s, disappearing into a "house"; 3 animals reappear.	3 sessions (10 Go trials, 10 No-Go trials per session). 3 sessions (5 trials each).
Zanto et al. [14]	2024	Flanker Task Stroop Task Working Memory Task	Inhibitory Control Inhibitory Control Working Memory	Assess inhibitory control by identifying the central arrow direction amidst distractors. Measure inhibitory control by identifying text color instead of word meaning. Measure working memory via reverse Corsi block-tapping task.	Five-arrow arrays (congruent/incongruent). Words representing colors (e.g., "red") displayed in congruent or incongruent colors. Squares illuminated in sequences, requiring participants to recall them in reverse order.	28 trials (50% congruent/incongruent). 40 trials (50% congruent/incongruent). Adaptive trials (set size increases after correct trials).
Zhang et al. [29]	2024	Stop Task Letter Memory Task Keep Task Dots Task	Inhibitory Control Working Memory Working Memory Cognitive Flexibility	Evaluate inhibition by stopping responses to a "beep" signal. Assess working memory updating. Evaluate working memory by tracking recent items in categories. Assess cognitive flexibility with rule switching.	Left/right arrows with "beep" stop signal. Letter sequences displayed, requiring sequential recall. Visual stimuli from 5 categories (e.g., colors, animals) displayed in octets. Sun/moon stimuli requiring same-side or opposite-side responses.	48 trials (16 per condition). 8 trials. 9 trials. 20 trials.